

Robust Design Principles to Evaluate Additive Manufacturing Capabilities

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Abstract

Additive manufacturing (AM) is generating a paradigm shift by expanding the manufacturing capabilities. However, quality of AM produced parts is dependent on a number of machine, geometry and process parameters.

The impact of inputs, such as the machine technology, the part orientation, the part location and the quality of the digital data, affects the AM outcomes drastically. A new user faces the problem of selecting optimal sets of input variables and therefore, it is necessary to support this selection process that is based typically in tacit knowledge of the machine operator or service suppliers.

The present research has proposed a “composite” methodology integrating Taguchi design of experiments, multi-objective optimization and statistical process control, to optimize the manufacturing process and fulfil multiple requirements imposed to an arbitrary geometry. This study provides a comparative assessment of AM technologies and optimal process parameters. During the experiment, three conflicting requirements were imposed to a case geometry. Two of them, at the macro level, evaluated dimensional and geometrical tolerances. The third one, at the micro level, evaluated the surface quality of the produced parts.

The outcomes of the experiment indicate that only one machine (M1, Stereolithography), was feasible to simultaneously fulfil macro and micro level requirements. In addition, the process was capable but not centred according to production standards. Future study including mechanical performance variables, interaction between variables and impact of noise factors is planned.

1. Introduction

Research evidences show that Additive Manufacturing (AM) technology can potentially replace conventional manufacturing methods (Campbell, et al., 2012). AM systems are capable to directly manufacture functional engineering components at low cost (Levy, et al., 2003). This could potentially limit the high initial investment in injection moulding tooling of small series production and therefore, reduce cost and time-to-market during the product development. Over the past years, mechanical properties of the materials as well as the reliability and re-

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peatability of AM processes have improved significantly. It is expected that AM systems will move soon from being a Rapid Prototyping (RP) tool to be a Direct Component Manufacturing (DCM) method (Wholers, 2013) and (Mellor, et al., 2013).

However, those expectations require significant developments on the technology. AM machines have different architectures and material processing capabilities. The characterization of the machines and materials is not yet mature and the differences are substantial in terms of achievable mechanical and dimensional properties (Clemon, et al., 2013). Technical parameters of the technology are not fully understood and capabilities have not yet been fully investigated by the engineering community (Gibson, et al., 2010).

Geometrical stability and material properties of AM produced part are strongly dependent on part geometry and machines parameters. Therefore, the final quality of the produced parts is subordinate to a list of variables including the machine and process variables. Research has indicated that the effect of the part orientation and the location on geometric stability of AM produced geometries need to be studied further to drive the technology to become a DCM method (Anand & Ratnadeep, 2011), (Brajlih, et al., 2010) and (Dimitrov, et al., 2003).

In addition, manufacturing community still faces basic problems when selecting the optimum AM technology and process parameters for DCM. For instance, Laser Sintering (LS), Stereolithography (SL) and Polyjet technology are some of the most promising alternatives to produce engineering functional parts, but the final quality of the produced parts changes substantially from technology to technology (Wholers, 2013).

Previous work has developed decision making tools for optimal AM systems selection, based on balancing the manufacturing cost, production capacity and quality (Williams, et al., 2003). Researchers have used Design of Experiments (DOE) to select optimum manufacturing parameters (Hsu & Lai, 2010), (Wang, et al., 2007) and (Rahmati, et al., 2007). However, these experimental methods have not been combined.

In practice, parts have to fulfil simultaneously different types of geometrical and dimensional requirements. Frequently, the manufacturing parameters can have contradictory influences on different requirements. Selecting an optimized combination of machine and process parameters for fulfilling simultaneously multiple requirements has still to be tackled. There is then a need to combine a systematic experimental approach with a multi-objective optimization, as proposed in similar manufacturing context (Konda, et al., 1999).

In this research, a predictive method is proposed to tackle this problem. Taguchi robust DOE is applied, and then combined with multi-objective optimization based on Pareto optimum and Statistical Process Control principles to evaluate the robustness of the manufacturing process (Montgomery, 1992). The aim is to assist the machine selection and optimum processes parameters to fulfil multiple requirements. The long term vision of this work is to develop a computer aided tool providing an automatic selection of manufacturing parameters, including machine technology, by analysing the technical requirements of the geometry to be produced.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Geometry of the Case Study

The geometry used for this experiment is a typical ABS injection moulded plastic part found in mass produced consumer devices, such as mobile phones. As a purely functional inner structural plastic part, the requirements in are exclusively dimensional and geometrical. The final produced sample requires very tight geometrical and dimension tolerances as well as good

surface quality in order to be feasible for the mechanic assembly of the product. The nominal size of the part is 68.12 mm x 37.24 mm x 14.85 mm and its theoretical volume is about 3308 mm³.

2.2 Methodology

The methodology used during this research is illustrated by the process diagram in Figure 1. Initial steps of the process imply to select the geometry and the material of the geometry. These parameters will guide the selection of suitable machine alternatives. In this DOE, the machine alternatives included three different process categories described in the ASTM, Standard Terminology for Additive Manufacturing Technologies, ASTM F2792 – 12a (ASTM, 2013).

Figure 1. Methodology and its process diagram

2.1.1 Selection of the performance variables, process variables and factor levels

This research has considered the following factors affecting to the AM process, which can be separated into three categories, Signal Factors, Noise Factors and Control Factors. Figure 2 shows the P-diagram of the explored variables.

Figure 2. Parameter diagram used during the DOE

The impacts of the noise factors have been omitted in this experimental set-up. A total of three performance variables and four process variables with three factor levels are included in the DOE. The first process variable (A) describes the machine and material selection, the factor levels of this DOE are explained in Table 1.

Table 1. Process variable (A), machine and material

Machine Specifications	M1	M2	M3
Machine supplier	3D Systems	Stratasys	EOS
Machine Type	Viper SI2	Objet 500	Formiga P110
Industrial Process Category	Stereo Lithography (SL)	Polyjet	Laser Sintering (LS)
ASTM Process Category	Vat Photo-polymerization	Material Jetting	Powder Bed Fusion
Layer Thickness (Z-Axis)	50 μm	30 μm	100 μm
Material	Accura 25 Plastic	ABS Like	PA2200

The second process variable (B) is the part orientation on the machine build platform, in which the geometries are manufactured in horizontal, vertical and diagonal orientation (i.e. diagonal 45 deg. from the XY plane which corresponds to the build tray of the AM machines). The third process variable (C) studies the effect of the part location on the machine over the manufactured part. In this case, the levels included parts printed on the top left, centre and bottom right of the build platform. The last process variable (D) studies the quality of the digital data, in which intentionally the cordal errors of the STL files are pre-established. All these variables behave in a non-linear manner. Thus, three levels have been selected per each process variable. The summary of the process variables and factor levels is explained in Table 2.

Table 2. Summary of process variable and control levels

Process variables		Level 1	Level 2	Level 3
A	Machine and Material	M1	M2	M3
B	Part Orientation	Horizontal	Vertical	Diagonal
C	Part Location	Top Left	Centre	Bottom Right
D	Digital Quality	High (0.001mm)	Medium (0.01mm)	Low (0.1mm)

Regarding the performance variables, three measurable variables are included in order to integrate typical manufacturing requirements present in Injection Moulded parts. The combination of these three requirements is an important constraint to the AM process. Two of them, at the macro level, the flatness (P1) and the distance from hole to hole (P2) studied the geometrical and dimensional stability of the produced parts. The last variable, at the micro level, measured the surface quality (P3) of the produced parts

Figure 3 makes a summary of the performance variables and their requirements, as well as the optimization objective per performance variable. P1 required having a dimensional tolerance lower or equal to 0.3mm. P2 required having a dimensional tolerance within the range of +/- 0.17 mm of the nominal value $D=37.55$ mm. P3 required to be lower or equal to $R_a = 0.8 \mu\text{m}$, equivalent to N5 quality in the ISO standard, Geometrical Product Specifications (ISO1101, 2012). The optimization objectives of these performances are the following, the Flatness (P1) should be minimized, the hole to hole distance (P2) should lead to a target value and the surface roughness (P3) should be minimized.

Performance Variables		Optimization Objective	Requirement
P1	Flatness (mm)	Minimize	0.3 mm (max.)
P2	Hole to hole distance D (mm)	On target	37.55 +/- 0.17 mm
P3	Surface roughness Ra (µm)	Minimize	0.8 µm (max.)

Figure 3. Optimization objective and schematic views of the performance variables, flatness (P1), hole to hole distance “D” (P2) and surface roughness (P3).

2.2.2 Definition of the Design of Experiment (DOE) and suitable Taguchi Orthogonal Array

When planning a DOE, several process variables or input factors can be varied simultaneously in a controlled manner in order to obtain reliable, repeatable and structured data. Therefore, the variance of the experiments can potentially be minimized and the obtained data can be used to predict causal relationships of the system. This idea was introduced by Fisher and is nowadays widely used in experimental sciences (Fisher, 1935). By approaching the presented experiment in a full factorial fashion, a total of $34=81$ potential experiments would have been performed, if only one variable was changed after the other. To simplify and limit the experimental approach and save time and resources, a Taguchi DOE was implemented. Taguchi methods allow to use set of orthogonal arrays specially created for automatically randomizing the experiments and to create an optimal DOE.

An L9 orthogonal array has been selected to drive the experiment. The Table 3 shows the Taguchi array used in the DOE. The columns represent the process variables and the rows correspond to the individual experiments.

Table 3. Taguchi L9 orthogonal array for the DOE

Exp.	A (Machine & Material)	B (Part Orientation)	C (Part Location)	D (Digital Quality)	Encoding of the Experiment
1	M1	Horizontal	Top Left	High	1HLH
2	M1	Vertical	Centre	Medium	1VCM
3	M1	Diagonal (45deg)	Bottom Right	Low	1DRL
4	M2	Horizontal	Centre	Low	2HCL
5	M2	Vertical	Bottom Right	High	2VRH
6	M2	Diagonal (45deg)	Top Left	Medium	2DLM
7	M3	Horizontal	Bottom Right	Medium	3HRM
8	M3	Vertical	Top Left	Low	3VLL
9	M3	Diagonal (45deg)	Centre	High	3DCH

2.2.3 Measurements and experimental set-up

The experiments in the L9 array were repeated three times to take into consideration the variance. In addition, each sample was measured twice per performance variable for integrating the variance of the measurement processes. However, more measurement repetitions would

be needed to improve the experimental set-up. Altogether, 54 measurements were taken, 6 measurements per each experiment. In the SPC capacity validation phase of the methodology, 3 more parts were produced per feasible solution and measured again using the same process described previously.

Figure 4 shows the picture of all samples number 1. In the top side of the picture the part code is shown. Each of the produced part had embossed digitally the part code to assure the traceability of the part during the whole experiment.

Figure 4. Manufactured sample 1 during the DOE

The measurement of the performance variables P1 and P2 was performed with an image based 3D laser coordinate measurement system, Nikon VMR-3020. The machine calculated the flatness by computing the differences in the vertical axis of the points described in Figure 3. Regarding the performance variable P2, the machine measured directly the distance between hole centres. Last measurement of the performance variable P3 was obtained by using a profilometer, Taylor-Hobson Surtronic 3 Roughness Gage, the measuring distance or sampling length for calculating Ra was set to 4mm shown in in Figure 3.

2.2.4 Multi-objective optimization and Statistical Process Control (SPC)

After obtaining the data, the next phase implies to compare all combination results of the model against the requirement of the system, by doing so an initial filtering of not feasible solutions is implemented. If results are obtained after this filter, there are potentially feasible solutions to manufacture the part within requirements. Otherwise, new machine alternatives or less restrictive requirements need to be considered (see process diagram in Figure 2).

In case of obtaining results after the filter, the dominance between solutions is studied. Pareto optimal solutions need to be non-dominated solutions, a pairwise comparison algorithm is used in this research to compute the Pareto optimal solutions (Miettinen, 1999).

The final step consisted on applying a SPC capacity test to the manufactured Pareto optimal solutions (Shewhart, 1986). This is performed to evaluate the robustness of the manufacturing process (i.e. robust to noise and deviations in the process). For that purpose, the standard ISO was used (ISO7870-2, 2013).

In this research the minimum level for an acceptable capability index was set to 1. Hence, the process is capable if $C_p > 1$, else the process is not capable. The higher the C_p value, the smaller the dispersion of the data is. C_p should be used in conjunction with C_{pk} to account for evaluate spread and centring. If $C_{pk} > 1$ then the process is centred, else is not centred. The larger is the C_{pk} , the less variation between the process output and specifications. C_{pk} and C_p will be equal when the process is centred on its target value. If they are not equal, the smaller the difference between these indices, the more centred the process is (Larsson, 2002).

3. Results

Figures 5, 6 and 7 display the response graphic of the performance variables P1, P2 and P3 respectively. The mean values, standard deviation and the requirements are represented per process variable and per factor level.

Figure 5. Response graphic of the performance variable P1 (Flatness)

Figure 6. Response graphic of the performance variable P2 (Hole distance)

Figure 7. Response graphic of the performance variable P3 (Surface quality)

Based on the results displayed in the response graphics, most of the combinations of process variables will not be feasible to produce the part within the manufacturing requirements. Nevertheless, certain combinations of the process variables could potentially be feasible to produce parts that fulfil the imposed requirements. In order to evaluate this possibility, an initial filtering of the objective function was implemented. The filter result in this DOE was a set of four theoretical solutions able to satisfy the requirements. The following move is to study if these

four solutions are Pareto optimal or non-dominated solutions. After studying the dominance between solutions, only three Pareto efficient solutions were potentially feasible to fulfil all the requirements simultaneously. The feasible solutions are displayed in Table 4.

Table 4. Feasible non-dominated solutions to manufacture the case geometry

Process variable	Solution 1	Solution 2	Solution 3
A (Machine and material)	A1 (M1)	A1 (M1)	A1 (M1)
B (Part Orientation)	B2 (Vertical)	B2 (Vertical)	B3 (Diagonal)
C (Part Location)	C2 (Centre)	C2 (Centre)	C2 (Centre)
D (Digital Quality)	D2 (Medium)	D3 (Low)	D3 (Low)

At this stage two AM processes, the material jetting (M2) and the powder bed fusion (M3) have been eliminated. In addition, the results indicate that only parts produced in the centre of the tray can satisfy the requirements of the system. Results also show that Vat Photo-polymerization (M1) is better than the two other processes for surface quality (P3) and as good as the best option for the two other performances (Flatness, P1 and hole distance, P2).

Figure 8. Representation of the mean value, standard deviation and requirements for the solution 1 and solution 3

Considering the set of 3 feasible solutions, the SPC capability analysis is performed. To drive this analysis, for simplification reasons, solution 2 has been ruled out and only solution 1 and 3 were manufactured and measured again. The initial evaluation of Figure 8 indicates that the mean value of solution 1 is within the requirements for all the performance variables. This is not the case for Solution 3, in which the mean value of the roughness is outside the requirements, thus the solution is not feasible. The last step as described in the process diagram of Figure 2 is to evaluate the capability of each solution (i.e. its robustness to deviations in the process).

Table 5. Capability analysis for the solutions 1 and 3

Solution 1	P1		P2		P3	
Cp	1.156	Capable	1.074	Capable	1.560	Capable
CpK	0.756	Not Centred	0.892	Not Centred	0	Not Centred
Mean	0.098		37.521		0.436	
Stdev	0.046		0.053		0.085	
Solution 3						
Cp	1.78	Capable	1.48	Capable	4.52	Capable
CpK	1.53	Centred	0.78	Not Centred	0	Not Centred
Mean	0.171		37.631		1.150	
Stdev	0.028		0.038		0.029	

The results of the ISO-SPC capability analysis are displayed in Table 5. Cp and CpK indexes of solution 1 show that the process is capable but not centred. This is due to a too high standard deviation of the measured sample. The mean values of solution 3 are within the limits for 2 performance variables but failed for the roughness requirement, thus manufacturing is not feasible despite the fact of being capable.

4. Discussion

The results of the research demonstrated that the implementation of DOE, Multi-objective optimization and SPC analysis can be combined effectively to assess Additive Manufacturing (AM) feasibility and robustness for Direct Component Manufacturing. The results demonstrate that machine and process parameters have a fundamental impact on the final outcome as described in (Anand & Ratnadeep, 2011), (Brajlih, et al., 2010) and (Dimitrov, et al., 2003). By looking at the response graphics, P3 (Surface Quality) was the most difficult requirement to satisfy, followed by P1 (Flatness) and P2 (Hole distance) and results of Pareto optimum show that only three solutions were theoretically feasible. Based on the validation phase and SPC results, only one solution was feasible and capable; however, the process was not centred.

To select optimum factor levels for the process variables, results show that only M1 was potentially feasible to fulfil all the requirements of the system. M2 had flatness values out of specification and the surface quality of M2 and M3 was not within requirements. Moreover, only parts produced vertically and diagonally could potentially be used, the part location had a major impact and only parts manufactured in the centre of the build platform were feasible for the manufacturing. Process variable C (Digital quality) was not critical; the effect of the digital quality is often visible in geometrical features, such as round surfaces. The selected performance variables did not measure this effect quantitatively, future research is planned to address this relationship.

To describe the research limitations, the experiment did not include interactions between process variables, such as orientation and part location. For instance, a Taguchi L18 can be implemented to improve the experimental quality and study variable interactions. In addition, the sample size to compute Cp and CpK capability indexes was too low, as officially a sample of 50 data sets is required. The impact of noise factors have not been evaluated quantitatively in this initial research, further analysis using signal to noises ratio and analysis of variance would be necessary to evaluate the robustness of the model. Future research is planned to address all these issues in a new extended methodology.

5. Conclusion

The proposed methodology based on robust design principles can be used to create design guidelines for machine users and increase the automation level of machine and process parameters selection. In the future, standardized SPC methods will need to be applied to evaluate the robustness of AM systems for direct component manufacturing method. Based on the results, typical requirements imposed to injection moulding plastic parts for consumer devices are challenging to fulfil by AM technology. Specially, AM surface quality hardly can compete with injection moulding, when the requirements are very tight.

In addition, full production feasibility and robustness cannot be yet met with AM technology when geometrical, dimensional and especially surface quality requirements are high. Future research is planned to evaluate robustness of AM systems by including interactions between variables, mechanical performance variables and the effect of noise factors associated with AM technology (e.g. environmental noise, deterioration noise and variation noise).

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